

भारतीय प्रबंध संस्थान बेंगलूर
INDIAN INSTITUTE OF MANAGEMENT
BANGALORE

Pursuing
Excellence in
Management
Research

Doctoral Programme in Management

Training Future Researchers and Academicians

VISION

To be a global, renowned academic institution fostering excellence in management, innovation and entrepreneurship for business, government and society

**NIRF
Ranked #2 in
Management**

Doctoral Programme in Management

A five-year full-time programme leading to PhD Degree that strives to:

- Provide rigorous training in cutting edge inter-disciplinary research in management, and
- Train the next generation of academics that can inspire future business leaders and policy makers.

Areas of Specialization

- Decision Sciences
- Economics
- Entrepreneurship
- Finance and Accounting
- Information Systems
- Marketing
- Organizational Behaviour and Human Resource Management
- Production and Operations Management
- Public Policy
- Strategy

Programme Highlights

- Two years of specialized Doctoral courses
- Structured progress towards degree
- One-on-One research experience with faculty
- Over 100+ full time faculty with international reputation
- Publications in leading international journals
- Access to leading journals and datasets
- **Over 300+ alumni working as faculty in leading institutes**
- **Over 60% recent graduates hired as faculty in IIMs**

RESEARCH FACILITIES

Centres of Excellence

- Management Communication
- Public Policy
- Capital Markets & Risk Management
- Corporate Governance & Sustainability
- Israel Centre
- Mizuho India Japan Study Centre
- NSRCEL - N S Raghavan Centre for Entrepreneurial Learning
- Software & IT Management
- Supply Chain Management
- Teaching & Learning

IIMB Initiatives

- Behavioural Sciences Lab
- Consumer Insights
- Data Centre & Analytics Lab
- Real Estate Research

Apply online at: <https://www.iimb.ac.in/doctoral-programme-admission>

For queries: Visit or contact us at:

 Admission: phdadm@iimb.ac.in
+91.80.2699 3013 / 3017

 Programme: doctoralprogramme@iimb.ac.in
+91.80.2699 3056

 Contact: marketing@iimb.ac.in
+91.80.2699 3382 / 2699 3383

For **WEBINARS** and **OPEN HOUSE** sessions

register at: <https://iimb.viewpage.co/IIMB--PhD>

Financial Support and Fellowships

- Full waiver of tuition fees.
- Monthly stipend of INR 42,000 for living expenses.
- Startup and contingency grants for computers, software, and books (upto INR 1 Lakh spread over two years).
- Single seater hostel accommodation is provided for five years of the programme.
- Travel grants to attend multiple international and national conferences (upto INR 3.6 Lakh).
- Several milestone-based awards and merit-based scholarships.

Decision Sciences

The Decision Sciences area carries out research in theoretical and applied statistics, optimization theory, business analytics, machine learning, artificial intelligence, big data methodologies, and related applications to management problems. Faculty work closely with both industry and government sectors and conduct theoretical and applied research across the entire decision sciences spectrum.

Jitamitra Desai

Professor; Chairperson, Decision Sciences,
IIMB Chair of Excellence

In a data driven world, our research in Decision Sciences is vital to developing solutions to a variety of business, government and societal challenges

Core Courses in Decision Sciences

- Probability Theory
- Mathematical Methods for Management Research
- Linear programming and Networks
- Nonlinear Programming
- Statistical Inference
- Multivariate Statistics
- Dynamic Programming
- Advanced Statistical Methods and Computing
- Integer Programming and Combinatorial Optimization
- Stochastic Models

Recent Dissertations

- 2022: Time Series Clustering, Testing of Memory in Time Series and Quantifying Dependence in Volatility of Financial Time Series Using Complex Network Theory
- 2021: Evaluation of Policies to Auction, Retain and Value Players Services in IPL and other Sports Tournaments
- 2021: Essays on Next Best Action in Digital Marketing Using Reinforcement Learning
- 2020: Some New Stochastic Processes with Applications in Finance and other Areas

Aishvarya, PhD scholar

Aishvarya's work is related to data-driven decision-making in the field of online sports regulation. Her thesis focuses on online fantasy sports - a booming industry that is very popular especially among youngsters.

Anchal Soni, PhD scholar

Anchal's research provides informed and calculated decision-making ability to the advisors of financial markets as well as other areas of research like climate and health sciences.

Md Shahrukh Anjum, PhD scholar

Shahrukh works on combinatorial optimization. Combinatorial optimization is used to develop efficient solutions for a variety of problems, including airline network problems, deciding which taxis in a fleet should be routed to pick up customers, and determining the optimal way to deliver packages.

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For more information visit us at:

Decision Science Faculty and PhD Research at IIMB:

<https://www.iimb.ac.in/decision-sciences>

https://www.iimb.ac.in/programmes/doctoral-programme/specializations/decision_sciences

To know more
join the webinar:

Finance & Accounting

Through their teaching, research, and professional activities, area faculty members aim to influence the theories of asset pricing, financial management, and financial reporting. Area faculty's research on fundamental questions in finance and accounting has been published in leading academic accounting journals. Some recent areas of interest include: Corporate Finance, Financial Management of Non-Corporate Sector, Asset Pricing, Capital Markets, Corporate Governance, Financial Institutions and Services, Market Microstructure, Risk Management, etc.

V Ravi Anshuman

*Professor in Finance & Accounting
Chairperson, Finance & Accounting*

Faculty in the Finance and Accounting area work on cutting edge research in areas related to corporate finance, asset pricing, and risk management in the banking and finance sector.

Srijith Mohanan, PhD scholar

In his thesis, Srijith formulates a new framework for the 'de-facto' assessment of creditor rights and applies it in the Indian context to analyse the impact of the IBC on the corporate credit market.

Velavan S, PhD scholar

In his thesis, Velavan explores how environmental performances of the target firms affect merger and acquisition decisions and results. He also examines the relationship between environmental performances and real earnings management activities of the firms.

Core Courses in Finance and Accounting

- Introduction to Asset Pricing Theory
- Corporate Finance 1
- Financial Econometrics
- Financial Mathematics and Computation
- Financial Derivatives
- Selected Topics in Empirical Corporate Finance Research
- Indian Financial Markets and Institutions
- Accounting Theory & Empirical Research
- Asset Pricing - II (Microfoundations of Finance)
- Banking Theory- Seminar
- Corporate Finance II
- Microeconomic Theory 1

Recent Dissertations

- 2022: Trading Volume and Dispersion of Signals
- 2022: Three Essays on the Financial Characteristics of Indian Private Firms
- 2021: CEO Traits, Broad Diversity, and Firm Investment Outcomes
- 2021: Essays on Financing Frictions and Demand for External Finance
- 2021: Essays on the Influence of Culture on Equity Markets

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<https://www.iimb.ac.in/finance-account>

<https://www.iimb.ac.in/programmes/doctoral-programme/specializations/finance-accounting>

To know more
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Organizational Behavior & Human Resources Management

The Doctoral Programme in Organizational Behaviour and Human Resources Management has faculty with multidisciplinary qualifications and competencies in Social Sciences, Psychology and Management. The area works on a variety of research topics including Achieving Competitive Edge through People, Cross Cultural Issues in Management, HRM in High-Tech Organizations and SMEs, Human Dimensions of Corporate Restructuring, Leadership and Leadership Development, Organizational Diversity and Inclusion Issues, Organizational Structure and Processes, Social Entrepreneurship, Talent Management, and Work-Life Balance and Integration.

Gopal Mahapatra

Chairperson, Organizational Behavior & Human Resources Management

The OBHRM area offers courses and does research and consultancy in the domains of management and leadership focused on deriving the best out of employees in organizations and institutions.

Anupama Kondayya, PhD scholar

Her research focuses on the indigenous medical system of Ayurveda and its encounters with the Western medical system during the colonial and post-colonial period. She believes her work will help us better understand how we can support medical pluralism for ensuring universal healthcare.

Rajashik Roy Choudhry, PhD scholar

Focuses on the coping mechanisms of organizations during and after unprecedented shocking events such as wars, pandemics and similar black swan events. His research can provide useful insights to organizations in building resilience for unforeseen events and times of turbulence.

Core Courses in Organizational Behavior & Human Resources Management

- Organization Theory
- Human Resource Management
- Organizational Behavior

Recent Dissertations

- 2022: 'Not mere silent partners' – Understanding the role of venture capitalists in human resource management of startups
- 2022: "Cyber" Connected?: Empirically Investigating Relatedness as a Motivational Need among Skilled Gig Workers
- 2021: Organizational Career Management Practices as a Predictor of Career Satisfaction and Intention to Quit: A Role Theory Perspective
- 2021: Identity Work of Individuals with Disparate Work Identities
- 2020: Dealing with the Stigma of Dirty work: The coping Mechanisms of Waste Pickers

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<https://www.iimb.ac.in/organizational-behavior-human-resources-management>

<https://www.iimb.ac.in/programmes/doctoral-programme/specializations/obhrm>

To know more
join the webinar:

Strategy

Faculty in the Strategy Area are interested in factors that influence the performance of firms. Topics of interest include the variety of activities that businesses internally undertake (e.g. mergers and acquisitions, innovation, diversification, internationalization) or are externally influenced by (e.g. regulation, regional ecosystem, stakeholders). Apart from the core area of strategic management, faculty are also interested in international business, strategic alliances, new product development, management of technology and innovation, and corporate governance. The area closely interacts with allied fields such as economics, sociology and organizational behaviour, and develops theories that help scholars, practitioners, and policymakers understand the drivers of firm performance.

Ganesh N Prabhu

Professor in Strategy
Chairperson, Strategy

Strategy faculty have authored papers in top-tier journals and also authored books on innovation and entrepreneurship. The area faculty have been involved in high value consulting and advisory services with several Indian, multinational and government organizations. Some are also Board members of companies and not-for-profit organizations, and serve on Advisory Bodies and Government Committees. The area has a vibrant doctoral programme which has graduated about 35 students who currently hold faculty positions across top business schools in India.

Vikas Namadeva Prabhu, PhD scholar

His dissertation research delves into the phenomenon called business ecosystems, attempting to understand how business ecosystems are orchestrated. His work connects with extant research and provides deeper insights into how to craft successful ecosystem strategies.

Gaurav G B, PhD scholar

His three-part thesis focuses on firm capabilities. For the vast majority of his research, rely on secondary data from diverse databases.

Veethica Smriti, PhD scholar

Her dissertation is about optimal distinctiveness in firm innovation and its implications for firm performance. She contends that firms can position themselves differently, along multiple dimensions, so that they can be similar to their competitors in one dimension while being dis-similar in another. She uses patent data from the medical device industry.

Core Courses in Strategy

- Statistics for Management Research
- Qualitative Research Methods
- Strategy Content (A)
- Strategy Classics
- Organizational Theory
- Econometrics I
- Strategy Process Research
- Strategy Content (B)

Recent Dissertations

- 2023: Essays on Board Structure, Interlocking and Director Networks
- 2023: Creativity in Strategic Thinking: Mind Wondering, Complexity, and Strategic Outcomes
- 2023: Essays on Internationalization, Corporate Governance, Ownership Networks, and Firm Performance
- 2021: Emergence of Electric Vehicle Ecosystem in India: A Longitudinal Study
- 2021: Study of Strategic Persistence

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Strategy Faculty and PhD Research at IIMB:

<https://www.iimb.ac.in/strategy>

<https://www.iimb.ac.in/programmes/doctoral-programme/specializations/strategy>

To know more
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Information Systems

The Information Systems Area at IIM Bangalore offers postgraduate courses on Management of IS & Technology, Artificial Intelligence, Managing Digital Transformations, Big Data, Machine Learning, Software Product Management and Introduction to Computing. Doctoral courses include IS Management, IS Research Foundations, IS Theory, and ICT for Development that familiarize students with the state-of-the-art research in the area. The IS area also leads the Centre for Software and IT Management for Conducting impactful activities related to research and practice.

Shankar Venkatagiri

Professor in Information Systems
Chairperson, Information Systems

Faculty in the IS area have published numerous articles in reputed international journals, presented at the top IS conferences across the globe, and received prestigious awards. Their research interests cover multiple contemporary topics such as social media, telemedicine, IT outsourcing, cloud computing, digital platforms, digital payments, e-government, etc.

Shubha Krishnamurthy, PhD scholar

Her research focuses on telemedicine, which involves delivering diagnosis and treatment using ICT. My thesis contributes to the literature on technology-in-use practices, which can inform the IT artifact design process for effective use of remote-service applications like telemedicine.

Sai Dattathrani, PhD scholar

Unpacks the nuances of 'agency', i.e., the ability to act, of traditional information technology, AI, and humans. In her thesis, she uses the understanding of these nuances to study how human-AI assemblages can be designed for effective decision-making.

Sowmya Kini B, PhD scholar

Her research interests are broadly in the domains of online platforms, trust, user behaviour, and digital business models, also investigates the circumvention of platforms by its users.

Core Courses in Information Systems

- Statistics for Management Research
- Mathematical Methods for Management Research
- Information Systems Management
- IS Research Foundations and Perspectives
- Information and communications technology for development
- Theoretical Analysis of Information Systems
- Recent Developments in Information Systems

Recent Dissertations

- 2023: Essays on the Agency of AI: Theory, Method, and Ethical Implications
- 2022: A Study of the Guardian Vendor Role in IT Multisourcing
- 2021: Social Media Affordance and the Structure of Public Discourse
- 2021: Examining as a Service – Duality of Software-as-a-Service (SaaS)
- 2021: Effect of Business - IT Alignment on IS Integration Success in M&As: A three-stage Alignment Model

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<https://www.iimb.ac.in/faculty-information-systems>

<https://www.iimb.ac.in/programmes/doctoral-programme/specializations/is>

To know more
join the webinar:

Economics

The Economics Area engages in research, teaching, external engagements, and media and policy outreach in a wide range of fields. These include Behavioral Economics, Development Economics, Game Theory, Industrial Organization, International Trade, Labour Economics, Monetary Economics and Public Economics.

Tirthatanmoy Das

Associate Professor in Economics
Chairperson, Economics

The Economics Area has a vibrant doctoral program, attracting candidates from reputed programs in Economics as well as other disciplines from universities and programs in India and abroad.

Core Courses in Economics

- Microeconomics I
- Macroeconomics I
- Maths for Economics
- Macroeconomics II
- Econometrics I
- Foundations of Applied Macroeconomics
- Microeconomics II
- Econometrics II
- Microeconomics III
- Econometrics III

Recent Dissertations

- 2023: Servicing of Manufacturing Industries
- 2022: Health Care Access and Demand: Role of Health Insurance and Health Services Trade
- 2021: Essays on Labour Markets, Business Cycles and Monetary Policy in India
- 2021: Essays on Indian Agricultural Exports Effect of Rural Roads and Geography Related Intellectual Property
- Rights on Agricultural Exports in India
- 2020: Essays in International Trade in Post Liberalization India

Banantika Datta, PhD scholar

Her thesis involves the nexus of trade and migration to address emerging issues such as services trade, free trade agreements, and the mobility of professionals - specifically health workers.

Muneer, PhD scholar

His research interests include the Economics of Education and Development Economics in general. His current research investigates some crucial and topical issues in education economics.

Satarupa Mitra, PhD scholar

Uses experimental methods to investigate risk preferences, exponential growth bias in predicting COVID cases, corrupt behaviour, and mental health of adolescent students.

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<https://www.iimb.ac.in/programmes/doctoral-programme/specializations/economics>

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Production & Operations Management

The Production and Operations Management addresses research issues related to manufacturing, services, and technology management. Specific themes, among others, for research include the following: Sustainable Operations, IT Services and Electronic, supply Chain Management, Healthcare and Services. Faculty and students also engage with the Supply Chain Management Centre at IIMB. The Centre brings together practitioners from leading organizations and IIMB's multidisciplinary faculty and students to identify, document, research, develop and disseminate best practices in Supply Chain Management.

Tarun Jain

Associate Professor in Production & Operations Management
Chairperson, Production & Operations Management

Faculty in the Production and Operations Management area work on a variety of research topics with their doctoral students, including strategic sourcing and procurement decisions in supply chain, behavioural operations, sustainable operations, and agricultural supply chain management.

Ayesha Arora, PhD scholar

In her thesis, she develops game-theoretic models to analyze the intensity of advertisements under browser settings that use ad-blocking mechanisms and only allow ads that follow a set of rules and do not cause discomfort to users. She also analyze whether government bodies should regulate the choice of ad-blocking mechanisms.

Ashish Singh Bhandari, PhD scholar

Her thesis topic is 'Impact of battery energy storage system on electricity generation through renewable and non-renewable energy sources'. Her work finds that balancing penalties act as a significant factor in preventing energy markets from the damaging effects of arbitrage and aggravated imbalances.

Core Courses in Production & Operations Management

- Stochastic Models in Operations
- Principles of Inventory Control
- Advanced Supply Chain Management
- Introduction to Game Theory
- Empirical Research in Operations Management
- Optimization Models in OM
- Probability Theory
- Microeconomics
- Linear Programming and Networks
- Statistics I
- Econometrics
- Operations Management (PGP Core)

Shubham Singh, PhD scholar

The key focus area of his research is to analyze the impact of supplier innovativeness in a supply chain network on the firm's innovation, and how different types of buyer-supplier relationships impact the innovation of the firm. He uses different empirical and analytical modelling tools to generate insights into how global supply chains work, and how firms need to design their supply base portfolio.

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<https://www.iimb.ac.in/production-operations>

<https://www.iimb.ac.in/programmes/doctoral-programme/specializations/production-operations-management>

To know more
join the webinar:

Entrepreneurship

The Doctoral Programme in Entrepreneurship covers research that spans a wide range of theoretical perspectives in entrepreneurship, research methods and tools, and specific topics covering different contexts in which the entrepreneurship phenomenon is observed and practiced. The coursework includes courses from allied disciplines like economics, strategy and organizational theory. Faculty members have the expertise and competence to guide research in areas such as: entrepreneurial cognition, entrepreneurial opportunities, entrepreneurship theory, high growth entrepreneurship, entrepreneurial networks, entrepreneurial ecosystems, and international entrepreneurship. The area also works closely with NSRCEL, which is a leading incubator in the country, to explore practice-relevant research questions as well as translate research into practice.

Prof. Dalhia Mani

*Professor in Entrepreneurship
Chairperson, Entrepreneurship*

From addressing micro questions such as how entrepreneurs identify opportunities to exploring macro questions such as ecosystem development, the multi-disciplinary research approach adopted by the Entrepreneurship area covers it all.

Manjunath AN, PhD scholar

His research is at the intersection of entrepreneurship and business history. He investigates how entrepreneurial actions bring about regional transformation. He deep dives into the history of the old Mysore region, hailed as an industrial pioneer in the 1950s.

Aman Bhuwania, PhD scholar

Points out that research on funding and VC funded firms has dominated Entrepreneurship research. But, given that only 27% of IPOs are VC funded, where do others get their "funding" from? Can ventures scale without capital?

Core Courses in Entrepreneurship

- Statistics for Management Research
- Entrepreneurship Classics: Entrepreneurship in the History of Ideas
- Contemporary Entrepreneurship – I
- Contemporary Entrepreneurship - II

Recent Dissertations

- Entrepreneurial Agency in Regional Transformation: An Entrepreneurial History of Old Mysore Region (1881-1956)
- Essays on Venture Learning within accelerators

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Entrepreneurship Faculty and PhD Research at IIMB:

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<https://www.iimb.ac.in/programmes/doctoral-programme/specializations/entrepreneurship>

To know more
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Marketing

The Doctoral Programme in Marketing focuses on a wide range of topics using a variety of research methods and tools. Faculty members have the expertise in a variety of areas including Product Management, Brand Management, Marketing Decision Models, Consumer Behaviour, Marketing Strategy, Services Marketing, Retailing, and Business to Business Marketing. The coursework includes courses on marketing management, marketing models, and research methods.

Sreelata Jonnalagedda

Professor in Marketing

Faculty in Marketing aims to construct a theoretical and empirical basis to understand the incentive structures that drive pricing (on the sellers' end) and purchase behavior (consumers' end). Structuring the price of innovative durable products, and understanding how bundles, retail prices and assortment choices influence consumer perceptions are among her research interests. Her wider areas of research include pricing, channel structures, information diffusion (word-of-mouth), and the application of gametheoretical modeling techniques to marketing problems.

Core Courses in Marketing

- Advanced Marketing Management
- Research Methods: Surveys and Experiments
- Marketing Models
- Research Perspectives in Consumer behaviour
- Marketing Models and Estimation
- Services Marketing

Recent Dissertations

- 2023: Exploring Emerging Market Heterogeneity
- 2023: Essays on Customer Experience in Access-Based Services
- 2022: Under the Influence - Three Essays on How Social Influence Impacts Behaviour on Online Platforms
- 2022: Cultural Effects on Perceived Affordances of Visual Branding
- 2021: Essays on Online Shopping Behaviour

Jose Manu M A, PhD scholar

His focus area is online review and growing importance of reviews on buying behaviour leading to a deeper understanding of customer engagement. In his thesis he tries to explore the effects of characteristics of online customer engagement, engagement with opinions that are made by social media in variety of ways, this includes liking, upvoting, commenting or sharing opinions. His research explores how and why customer engagements occur and how the presence of others in the network motivates customers to engage in online review.

Findings of the study are expected to contribute to the literature on customer engagement legally and eventually higher level of customer engagement preferably with positive values.

Dhriti Mahadevan, PhD scholar

Conceptualises and identifies specific drivers of customer experience for access-based services like Uber, AirBnB, Swiggy, Zomato etc. She uses her framework to investigate how the interactions between customers, platform and third-party providers affect the overall customer experience, which in turn affects the performance of both the third-party providers as well as the platform.

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Public Policy

The Doctoral Programme in Public Policy focuses on research in public policy analysis, design, process and management. Doctoral level courses cover research that spans a wide range of sectors and policy areas. Faculty members have the expertise and competence to guide research in areas such as: Agriculture and Rural Development, Democracy and Decentralization, Environment/Ecological Economics, Policy Modelling, Institutional Structure and Effective Governance, Public Finance, Regulation, Urban Governance, Public Private Partnership, Political Economy, Gender and Development. Students and faculty actively engage with the Centre for Public Policy at IIMB.

Arnab Mukherji

Professor in Public Policy

Agriculture, Financial Inclusion, Education, Health, Human Development in Urban & Rural areas, Livelihoods... are some of the key focus areas of the Centre for Public Policy and the PhD Programme it offers.

Tanieem Noor Darvesh, PhD scholar

Her research focuses on women's empowerment and economic growth, a key sustainable development goal. The objective of her research is to establish channels that may be used to progress towards this goal"

Deepti Sharma, PhD scholar

Her focus on the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on households' economic well-being and their recovery mechanisms, including the use of insurance, credit and other financial instruments.

Core Courses in Public Policy

- Statistics for Management Research
- Public Policy Analysis
- Public Administration and Law
- Comparative Politics for Public Policy
- Social Theory for Framing Research
- Development Studies
- Qualitative Methods
- Microeconomics I | PGP Managerial Economics (either)
- Econometrics I
- Econometrics II

Recent Dissertations

- 2023: Institutional Design for Market Participation and Livelihood Security of Smallholder Farmers:
- Case Study of an Agricultural Marketing Cooperative
- 2023: Essay on Economics of Poor Environment
- 2022: Cropping Pattern and the Human-Elephant Conflict in South India
- 2022: Implications of Emerging Technologies on the Indian Information Technology Sector and Beyond
- 2021: Essays on the Plural Logics of Regional Development

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<https://www.iimb.ac.in/programmes/doctoral-programme/specializations/public-policy>

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International Accreditation

1 FT MiM Global Rankings 2022: #1 in India; #31 globally

1 Eduniversal 2023: #1 B-School in Central Asia Gold Trophy & 5 Palmes

1 QS World University Rankings 2024 (PGP & EPGP): #1 in India; In the Top 50 globally

1 QS EMBA Rankings 2023: PGPEM is #1 in India; #16 in APAC; #43 globally

1 Bloomberg Best Business-Schools Survey 2023: 1-yr EPGP is #1 in India; #4 APAC

1 FT EMBA 2023: #1 in India; #94 globally

2 India Rankings 2023, Management Category (by Ministry of Education, Govt): #2 in India

3 FT MBA 2024: #3 in India; #47 globally

Global Networking

FT Executive Education: In Global Top 50 in 2023, 2022, 2021 & 2020

In the Top of the Positive Impact Rating 2023 with the moniker 'Pioneering School'

Only Indian B-school in the Global Network for Advanced Management

Featured Among the Leading B-Schools Globally

Why Bangalore is ideal for living and learning - Bangalore, one of Asia's fastest growing cosmopolitan cities, is among India's best places to live in. It has become synonymous with disruptive innovation and entrepreneurship. As the start-up hub of India, it is also a happy talent hunting ground for companies including Airbus, Amazon, Flipkart and InMobi. It is a new-age city that has retained some of its old world charm and enjoys a fabulous climate.

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